

ENHANCING SOCIOCULTURAL COMPETENCE IN MIDDLE SCHOOL LEARNERS USING PROJECT-BASED LEARNING

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***Abstract.** This article is devoted to defining the place and role of the project method in the process of improving sociocultural competence in secondary school at the lessons of foreign languages. Besides, the article dwells upon different stages of the project work and necessary conditions of the effective use of this method.*

***Keywords.** Sociocultural competence, project method, students of primary and secondary schools, foreign language methodology.*

Introduction. Proponents of individual differences acknowledge aptitudes, skills and preferences inherent to learners. The complexity of learning is reflected in these differences: An individual must be willing or motivated to learn; he or she must be able to learn; the environment must foster learning; and the instruction must be effective for the learner. There is no unique accepted definition of PBL. However, BIE defines standards-focused PBL as a systematic teaching method that engages students in learning knowledge and skills through an extended inquiry process structured around complex, authentic questions and carefully designed products and tasks. This definition encompasses a spectrum ranging from brief projects of one to two weeks based on a single subject in one classroom to yearlong, interdisciplinary projects that involve community participation and adults outside the school. More important than the definitions are the attributes of effective projects. The BIE planning model is based on a number of criteria that distinguish carefully planned projects from other extended activities in the classroom.

Main part. The socio-cultural component highlighted in the content of foreign language teaching includes the following knowledge.

1) Cultural awareness of the socio-cultural portrait of English as the language of international communication;

2) Knowledge about the cultural heritage of English-speaking countries and their contribution to the development of world culture, knowledge of the social system of the country/countries of the studied language, knowledge of national realities, the most important historical events;

3) Knowledge of the greatest figures of literature and art, politics and diplomacy;

4) An idea of the pan-European and national cultural background of modern traditions and values;

5) Knowledge of norms of behavior and etiquette, including methods of verbal and non-verbal contact, and skills of socio-cultural behavior, including skills of verbal and non-verbal methods of contact.

Early in the last century, Dewey (1938) and Vygotsky (1962; 1978) encouraged experiential learning, providing the theoretical foundations for project-based learning. More recently, Brown, Collins and Duguid (1989) and Lave (1990) have proposed learning is contextualized for individuals. Through interactions with the environment, including people and technologies, individuals create meaning.

Conclusion. The variety of ways in which the five students in this case study developed their learning artifacts offers three significant implications for practitioners and researchers. First, sustained project-based learning is a not a simple task for teachers nor students. It is essential for teachers to comprehend how students will perform in these learning environments and recognize students may be ill prepared. Hill and Hannafin (2001) suggest that students with primarily didactic, teacher-directed experiences may not have the skills necessary to work within more open-ended learning environments. Knowledge and skills such as metacognition and self-regulation may be beyond the students' reach. Bob and

Allison demonstrated the strongest uses of metacognitive knowledge, but they were limited in recognizing how it helps them.

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